

[PART 1: BACKGROUND + EMAIL EXPERIENCE] (5 mins)

1. Can you briefly describe your experience as:
 - Developer or Reviewer
 - Have you used GitHub Pull Request notifications via email?
 2. When you receive a GitHub notification email, what do you usually do?
 - Do you read the comment?
 - Do you open the PR immediately?
 - Do you ignore it until you have more time?
 - Do you delete/archive without reading?
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[PART 2: LL.M. CLASSIFICATION SCENARIO INTRO] (5 mins)

Introduce the setup:

“We’re experimenting with an LLM-based tool that classifies PR comments in GitHub notification emails as *important* or *ignorable*. The goal is to help recipients—especially those who aren’t the original author or main reviewer—decide faster whether they need to take action.”

3. Before seeing examples, how do you feel about AI classifying comment importance in PR emails?
4. Would you want to know which comments are *not important* before even opening the PR?

[PART 3: SCENARIO EVALUATION WITH EMAIL MOCKUPS] (15 mins)

- Would you click the PR link?
- Would you feel this comment needs your attention?
- How would you respond to it (if at all)?

- Was the LLM label helpful?
6. If both emails arrived in your inbox—one with LLM classification, one without—**which one would you act on first, and why?**

[PART 4: NASA TLX – Perceived Effort Comparison] (5 mins)

From 1 to 10

7. How mentally demanding was it to decide whether to read or ignore the PR?
8. How confident were you in your decision?
9. How much effort did you put into assessing the importance of the comment?
10. How frustrated (if at all) did you feel?

[PART 5: OPEN FEEDBACK & DISCUSSION] (5 mins)

11. Do you think LLM-marked PR comments in email would change your workflow?
12. What would make you trust (or distrust) such a system?
13. What improvement do you wish to see in future versions?
14. Would you want this system deployed in your team's daily practice?